

NEXOGENESIS

STREAMLINING WATER RELATED POLICIES

Deliverable 1.3

Policies for the Self Learning Nexus Assessment Engine (SLNAE)

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Abstract

As part of the activities of T1.4, this deliverable (D1.3) presents the policies (i.e. policy instruments) for the Self-learning Nexus Assessment Engine (SLNAE). The policy instruments presented along with an illustration of the stakeholders co-creation and validation process. In the coming months the case studies will discuss the policy instruments presented in this report with WP3 and WP4 to identify those that are feasible, from a data and modelling perspective, to integrate in the SLNAE and for which targets and indicators will be defined/finalized. This process will result in the final set of policy instruments, goals, objectives and related targets and indicators to be integrated in the SLNAE and whose impact on the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) nexus the stakeholders will be able to explore with the SLNAE.

Keywords

Policy instruments, policy packages template, Self-learning Nexus Assessment Engine, stakeholders, co-creation

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Executive summary

As part of the activities of T1.4, this deliverable (D1.3) presents the policies (i.e. policy instruments) validated with the stakeholders in each NEXOGENESIS Case Study (CS) and an illustration of the co-creation and validation process. In the coming months the CSs will discuss the policy instruments presented in this report with WP3 and WP4 to identify those that are feasible, from a data and modelling perspective, to integrate in the Self-learning Nexus Assessment Engine (SLNAE) and for which targets and indicators will be defined/finalized. This process will result in the final set of policy instruments and related targets and indicators to be integrated in the SLNAE and whose impact on the WEFE nexus the stakeholders will be able to explore with the SLNAE. The results of the impact assessment of these policies on the WEFE nexus in each CS region will provide the basis for the dialogue among the local stakeholders on what set of policies is desirable and agreeable by all stakeholders to improve WEFE nexus governance in their region.

To help the CS leads identify preliminary policy instruments to discuss with stakeholders, WP 1, in collaboration and after discussions with WP2, WP3 and WP4, designed the so called “policy packages” template and outlined the process to co-create and validate the policies together with the local stakeholders. The identification of the policy instruments builds on insights from the policy coherence analysis and governance assessment in each CS (see details in D1.2) along with bilateral and group discussions with stakeholders at the NEXOGENESIS workshops in the context of task 1.4.

Note to the reader: the consortium decided to rename the SLNAE into Nexus Policy Assessment Tool (NEPAT) in communication with stakeholders to make it more intuitive for them to understand what the tool is about, and to keep using the old name in deliverables to maintain consistency with the Grant Agreement. Accordingly, in this deliverable we will continue to use the original name SLNAE. More detailed explanation about the name change can be found in the M18 project review report.

Contribution to EU policies

This deliverable is a crucial step in the overall NEXOGENESIS process as it presents the selected policies whose impact on the WEFE nexus in the case study regions can be assessed through the SLNAE. The selected policies relate to various EU policies, including the Water Framework Directive, the Common Agricultural Policy and the Renewable Energy policy. The assessment of the impact of the selected policies will ultimately lead to better understanding the interaction between these policies, not only at the local level but also at EU level. It will also provide insights on how local and regional policies contribute to EU policy goals. Moreover, it will give direction on a combination of policies that can lead towards improved WEFE nexus governance both at local/regional and EU level. Finally, all the above insights will be available also for the two transboundary case studies, thus contributing to the EU’s water diplomacy discussion.

Related Deliverables

D1.1 Stakeholders’ co-creation approach for WEFE nexus Governance (M12)

D1.2 Governance and policy assessment in case studies (M25)

D3.4 Complexity science models implemented for all the Case Studies - Prototypes and explanatory report/manual for each CS (M23)

D3.6 Sensitivity/Uncertainty Analysis Report (M30)

D4.2 Data Lake for data sharing (M32)

D4.3 Simulation policy framework (M34) D4.4 Core module of the self-learning nexus engine (M34)

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Abbreviations

CS	Case Study
D	Deliverable
M	Month
WP	Work Package
WEFE Nexus	Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem nexus
SLNAE	Self Learning Nexus assessment Engine
NEPAT	Nexus Policy Assessment Tool
PNIESC	National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030
PNS	the Common Agricultural Policy National Strategic Plan 2023-2027

1. Introduction

WP1 has designed a stakeholders' co-creation approach towards WEFE nexus governance (D1.1 and Figure 1) that aims to support stakeholders in the NEXOGENESIS case study (CS) regions to identify and agree on relevant policies for improved WEFE nexus governance. There are five CSs in the project covering 5 river basins: Nestos-Mesta (Greece-Bulgaria), Lielupe (Lativa-Lithuania), Adige (crossing two autonomous provinces and one region in Italy); Jiu (Romania); and Inkomati-Usunthu (the river basin is transboundary but the project focuses on South Africa).

The stakeholders' co-creation approach aims to support stakeholders to develop a shared understanding of problems for the river basin and accordingly design the building blocks of an agreement for actions to implement in the basin; ideally at least in one case studies stakeholders will be also able to reach such agreement. NEXOGENESIS defines such a stakeholder agreement as a voluntary, negotiated action plan developed through a stakeholders' co-creation process where relevant stakeholders across the WEFE sectors identify actions for the management of the (transboundary when relevant), cross-sectoral WEFE resources. The stakeholders involved in the process commit and take responsibility, each within their respective frame of roles and competences, for the adoption and implementation of a set of agreed actions for the integrated management of the WEFE resources in the river basin as well as for the monitoring of the implementation. Actions can be of any sort and at any scale, from joint cleaning up of the river, to data sharing or fostering the adoption/change of specific policies.

Figure 1 Stakeholders co-creation approach towards WEFE nexus governance

The selection of the policies (i.e. policy instruments) for the SLNAE for each CSs is a central step in this process. These policies should reflect the needs of the stakeholders. Therefore, the process of co-creation is based on intense exchange with stakeholders via the

NEXOGENESIS workshops and bilaterally with the CS leads (WP5), as well as on insights gathered during the WEFE nexus governance assessment interviews and the policy coherence assessment reported in D1.2. Furthermore, these policies have to be linked to the CSs conceptual models implemented in the CSs System Dynamic Models (SDMs) by WP3 and later on implemented into the SLNAE by WP4. Therefore, the timely delivery of the policies for the SLNAE is crucial to ensure the success of the whole SLNAE development process. To timely provide the policies for the SLNAE to WP3 and WP4, WP1, in collaboration with WP3 and WP4, designed the so called “policy packages” template, outlined the process to populate it and supported CSs throughout the process of populating the template.

This deliverable presents the template, the stakeholder co-creation process, and the stakeholders validated policy instruments. As next step, CS leads will discuss the selected policies with WP3 and WP4 in terms of data availability and modelling feasibility, and for the feasible policies they will identify/finalize targets and indicators.

2. Methods

The CS leads identified the policy instruments for the SLNAE in close collaboration with WP1. Several steps were taken between January 2022 and July 2023 to this purpose.

First, WP1 developed the policy inventory and conducted, together with the CS leads, the policy coherence assessment (see D1.2) between January 2022 and May 2023. The policy inventory consists of an Excel database in which the CS leads reported all WEFE nexus policies relevant to their case study along with key information such as year of adoption, time horizon of the policy, scale of the policy, goals of the policy and instruments adopted by the policy. The case study leads had to assess the level of coherence of each identified policy with the other nexus sectors (i.e. no coherence, little coherence, high coherence) and explain where the coherence (or lack thereof) was found in the policy document in terms of prescriptions to mitigate negative impacts on other sectors or exploit potential synergies with other sectors (i.e. no prescriptions even if impacts/synergies exists; only mentioning impacts/synergies but no mandatory actions; mandatory actions to mitigate impacts/exploit synergies). This exercise helped the CS leads to have an overview of the relevant existing policies and their level of coherence which is a key characteristic of WEFE nexus governance. Through workshop (WS)1, WS2 and focus groups the policy coherence assessment was validated and stakeholders' initial preferences for policy instruments were gauged. The interviews conducted for the WEFE nexus governance assessment in each CS also provided insight into the preferences of stakeholders for policy instruments.

Second, WP1 designed the so called “policy packages” template in January 2022 (see Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4) to be filled in by the CS leads. The template includes 3 parts:

- 1) The policy instruments to include in the SLNAE (Figure 1); the selection of the instruments was led by the CSs, supported by WP1, and done in close collaboration with stakeholders;
- 2) The data needs, model assumptions and variables affected by the policy instruments (Figure 2); this part of the process is done by CS leads with WP3 and WP4 and may lead to changes in the policy instruments to include in the SLNAE, depending on model/data feasibility;
- 3) The goals, objectives and targets associated with each of the selected and feasible policy instrument (Figure 3); this part of the process is done by CS leads with support of WP1 and WP3 after the final set of feasible policy instruments have been selected.

Step 2 and 3 of the process are beyond the scope of this deliverable and are related to D3.4, D3.6, D4.2, D4.2 and D4.4. The template and methodology were presented to the CSs and WPs during the general assembly in September 2022 in Riga.

Then, WP1 and the CS leads had bilateral meetings between September and November to discuss initial ideas of how to fill in the template. Moreover, there were regular check-in moments on the process of filling in the template during the consortium co-creation meetings.

Finally, between November 2022 and July 2023 the CS leads synthesized the policy discussions they had with their stakeholders and started populating the template. This resulted in a preliminary set of policy instruments which was then discussed with the stakeholders during WS3 for validation between March and July 2023.

In the coming months, the CSs and WP3 will discuss the feasibility of integrating the selected policy instruments into the System Dynamic Models (SDMs) and the SLNAE based on available data. This will lead to the final set of policy instruments for which the CSs will define/finalize targets and indicators. The result of this process and the final set of policy instruments, targets and indicators will be then shared with the stakeholders accompanied with explanation of the rationale that led to it. It is relevant to point out that some CSs, have already started identifying and discussing with stakeholders targets and indicators during the process of selecting policy instruments, ahead of schedule, so as to enhance the feasibility of policy instruments envisaged at this stage.

Template for policy packages: from policies to models

TO BE DISCUSSED WITH STAKEHOLDERS (CSs WITH SUPPORT WP1, WP3)

	Sector that adopt/implement the policy (WEFE, others)	Existing vs. desired policy	Policy instrument	Scale of implementation (entire river basin or sub-basin): only for Lielupe and Nestos; Adige
Example	Agriculture	Existing	Subsidies to farmers for adoption of efficient irrigation technology	Greece part of the basin
				Bulgaria part of the basin
				Entire river basin
	Agriculture	Existing	Subsidies to farmers to switch to low water demand crops	Entire river basin
	Agriculture	Desired	Investments to (repair) renovate water infrastructures	Entire river basin

Figure 2 Policy packages template: policy instruments data

Figure 2 shows the first part of the policy package template, the one that collects the policy instruments data. Here information is reported on the sector that implements the policy, whether it is an existing or desired policy, the policy instrument, and lastly the scale of implementation. The scale is particularly relevant to the transboundary CSs and the Adige case study. These CSs can choose to apply the policy instrument only in one part of the basin (country or administrative region/province in Italy) or in the entire river basin. This choice has implications for the impact of the policy instruments.

Template for policy packages: from policies to models															
TO BE DEVELOPED BY CSs WITH WP3, WP4, WP2															
Entry sector of the policy in the conceptual model (WEFE, others)	Assumptions to be made to translate policy into models	Modulation of the instrument (range or fixed value)	Specific assumptions on the changes triggered by the policy instrument in the model variables	Input variables used in models to implement policy	Data	link to other sectors	Variables in the models affected by the policy across all nexus sectors	Delay of implementation (start of effects of the policy)	Duration of implementation	Policy effect is permanent? Yes/no	Policy can be applied more than ones? Yes/no	If applied multiple times, indicate effectiveness reduction	Policy cost (token): low/medium/high	Potential source of funding for the specific policy instrument (from policy documents or there is none; eg EU recovery fund)	Social acceptance of policy instrument (token): low/medium/high

Figure 3 Policy packages template: data requirements, assumptions and variables for the modeling of the policy instruments in the SDM and the SLNAE

Policy goals, objectives and related targets + indicators for the models							
TO BE DEVELOPED BY CSs WITH SUPPORT WP1 and WP3					TO BE DEVELOPED BY CSs WITH WP3, WP4, WP2; ; each CS has its own set of nexus performance indicators		
Sector	Policy goal (derived from existing policies or more ambitious than existing policies)	Target associated to policy goal (value and timeframe)	Policy objectives that contribute to achieve the goal (as found in existing policies or more ambitious)	Target associated to objective	Indicators (derived from existing policies or defined by CSs and WPs)	Input to the model (WP2 and WP3)	Output of the model (make it as close as possible to the indicator)

Figure 4 Policy packages template: goals, objectives, targets and indicators for each policy instrument

3. Results

This section presents the stakeholder validated policy instruments for the SLNAE of the five CSs accompanied by a description of how they were selected. Some CSs (Inkomati and Adige) also initiated an internal discussion on the policy goals, targets and indicators associated to those policy instruments and started collecting preliminary feedback from the stakeholders. These preliminary, goals, targets and indicators are not included in this deliverable, which is concerned only with the validated policy instruments, as mentioned in the previous section. The finalization of goals, targets and indicators will take place after the final set of policy instruments for the SLNAE will be selected in dialogue with WP3 and WP4 and will be relevant for the activities that will be reported in D3.4, D3.6, D4.2, D4.2 and D4.4.

3.1 Case study 1 Nestos-Mesta

The design of the Nestos-Mesta case study policy instruments for the SLNAE started with an exploration of existing policies and legislations relevant to the WEF nexus in both Greece (GR) and Bulgaria (BG). A policy inventory was created that includes the policy goals, instruments, and an assessment of the policy coherence with the respective nexus sectors.

The main pressures and existing problems of the Nestos-Mesta river basin were discussed at a first stakeholder workshop in March 2022, so as to gather input from the stakeholders on relevant policies, which took place separately in the two countries involved in the CS, i.e., one (first) workshop was held in Greece in the Nestos municipality and another (first) one in Bulgaria in Gotse Delchev municipality. The governance assessment that followed (performed in July 2022), provided further input on the existing pressures and problems in the Nestos-Mesta river basin and the existing governance and policy structure.

Based on the input from both workshops and the governance assessment, the CS leads developed a preliminary list of policy instruments. This preliminary list was presented to the stakeholders during the second stakeholder workshop(s) (again held separately), in both Greece and Bulgaria in November 2022. During this workshop, stakeholders were asked to comment on the preliminary policy instruments and to express their preferences. This workshop helped to further specify the policy instruments that would fit the local context and stakeholders needs resulting in a final draft.

In March 2023 the 3rd, transboundary, stakeholder workshop was held to present the final draft of the policy instruments to both the Greek and Bulgarian stakeholders. During this workshop, the stakeholders discussed the policy instruments and provided additional reflections and feedback that were used to create the final, validated set of policy instruments, presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Stakeholders validated policy instruments for the Nesto/Mesta case study

Sector that adopts/ implements the policy	Existing vs. desired policy	Policy instrument	Scale of implementation
Water	Desired	Change of irrigation systems/practices (furrow, sprinkler, drip) - Investments	Entire basin
Water	Existing	Monitoring/measuring the quantity of pesticides/toxic substances discharged in the river	Entire basin
Water	Existing	Flood-preventing infrastructures; Proactive assessment of flood risk	Entire basin
Water	Existing	Waste-water treatment plants / technologies	Mostly BG sub-basin
Water	Desired	Monitoring volumes of water coming from the Bulgarian side	GR sub-basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Reforestation ; register of wetlands	GR sub-basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Securing the minimum % of ecological flow	Entire basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Characterization of areas as: strict nature reserves, nature reserves (protected areas), natural parks (national/regional), protected habitats (special preservation zones, areas of special protection, habitats of wildlife or combination of all the above), protected landscapes	Entire basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Protection of biodiversity from intensive agriculture / expansion of agricultural land	Entire basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Inventory of biodiversity threats/pressures	Entire basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Definition of specific indicators	Entire basin
Food	Desired	Cultivation of dynamic crops aromatic and pharmaceutical herbs, whortleberry, pomegranate, sea buckthorn, tobacco, legumes, honey, wine	GR sub-basin
Food	Desired	Livestock products, greenhouse crops, arboriculture, vegetables, agro-forestry. Local pillars: honey, grapes, winery	GR sub-basin
Food	Desired	Protection of pastures	GR sub-basin
Food	Existing	Increase aquaculture production	GR sub-basin
Energy	Existing	Energy production from geothermal, P/Vs, wind turbines	Entire basin
Energy	Existing	Energy production from biomass, agricultural waste combustion (GR), composting (BG) and energy crops	Entire basin
Energy	Existing	Electricity production from water available in dams	Entire basin

3.2 Case study Lielupe

The Lielupe policy instruments for the SLNAE were designed through an iterative co-creation process with stakeholders from Latvia (LV) and Lithuania (LT) in several workshops. As in the other case studies, the process started with the policy inventory.

During the first stakeholder workshop in February 2022 (online) the stakeholders discussed key policies and their impact on the WEFE nexus, climate, and land use sectors in the Lielupe river basin. Stakeholders from both LV and LT attended the workshop. The stakeholders were split into four smaller groups where each participant was asked to reflect on a preliminary list of policy instruments prepared by the CS leads.

During the second stakeholder workshop held in Riga in November 2022, Latvian stakeholders identified the policy instruments that they considered the most effective to improve integrated resource management and reach the policy goals relevant for the Lielupe river basin. Based on the outputs of these discussions, the CS leads drafted the concept set of policy instruments. The set of proposed policy instruments covers all WEFE nexus sectors. Specifically:

- **Water** policy instruments include measures to decrease Nitrogen and Phosphorous and to reduce water pollution from urban areas such as requirements for buffer strips along water bodies, subsidies for application of precise fertilization technology, subsidies for improved operation of WWTP - tertiary water treatment in larger agglomerations, and subsidies for the construction of nature-based solutions e.g., constructed wetlands for smaller agglomerations.
- **Energy** policy instruments relate to increasing differentiation of energy sources in the energy mix and to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from (heat) energy consumption. The policy instruments include support schemes for installation of solar (PV) technologies in small-scale applications and for wind energy production at large commercial applications; introduction of regulatory policy instrument - revenue for municipalities from energy production from renewable energy sources could promote interest of local authorities to allocate areas for renewable energy production; and financial support to increase energy performance of buildings and to introduce energy efficient technologies for industry shall promote reduction of energy consumption in the territory.
- **Food** policy instruments aim to improve soil fertility and agricultural yield by increasing the share of organic farming and include measures such as: regulatory instruments prescribing requirements for application of fertilizers, crop rotation, alternated agricultural practices (e.g., minimal tillage); financial instruments including subsidies for organically grown products to compensate for reduced production compared to conventional farming, and support for dairy cattle farming; sewage sludge to increase fertilization of soils with organic matter.
- **Ecosystem** policy instruments include measures to ensure sufficient ecological flow in rivers and increasing land areas in optimum moisture conditions such as: subsidies for removal of obstacles/wastes in water bodies, cleaning of riverbeds, the development of constructed wetlands and improving the drainage system performance.

The draft set of policy instruments was discussed with Lithuanian and Latvian stakeholders during the third stakeholder workshop in June 2023 in Vilnius. During this workshop, the stakeholders validated the applicability of the proposed policy instruments in the Lielupe river basin. Some additional instruments were suggested, and their potential impacts, effects and trade-offs were identified.

After this initial discussion, the stakeholders were asked to select instruments for each WEFE nexus policy sector to be included in the SLNAE through a voting system. The voting results showed shared priorities for water – food nexus and different priorities for the energy-ecosystem nexus. The results of the workshop led to the stakeholders validated policy instrument presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Stakeholders validated policy instruments for the Lielupe case study

Sector that adopts/ implements the policy	Existing vs. desired policy	Policy instrument	Scale of implementation
Agriculture	Existing	Regulatory requirements for buffer strips along water bodies	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Existing	Subsidies for application of precise technologies for fertilization	LV and LT part of the basin
Land-use	Existing	Subsidies for improved operation of WWTP - tertiary water treatment in larger agglomerations	LV and LT part of the basin
Land-use	Desired	Subsidies for introduction of nature-based solutions e.g. constructed wetlands for smaller agglomerations	LV and LT part of the basin
Energy	Existing	Subsidies for installation of Solar (PV) for small-scale applications	LV and LT part of the basin
Energy	Existing	Subsidies for wind park erection for large commercial application	LV and LT part of the basin
Energy	Desired	Revenue for municipalities from energy production from RE technologies in their respective administrative territories	LV and LT part of the basin
Energy	Desired	Subsidies for production of biomethane (2nd generation biofuel)	LV and LT part of the basin
Energy	Existing	Subsidies for increasing energy performance of buildings	LV and LT part of the basin
Energy	Existing	Subsidies for introduction of energy efficient technologies for industry (boiler houses)	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Existing	Requirements for application of fertilizers	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Desired	Subsidies for biologically grown products to compensate for reduced production compared to conventional farming	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Existing	Requirements for crop rotation, e.g., legumes	LV and LT part of the basin

Agriculture	Desired	Subsidies for fertilization with organic matter e.g., support for dairy cattle farming, sewage sludge	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Existing	Requirements for alternated agricultural practices e.g., minimal tillage	LV and LT part of the basin
Water	Desired	Subsidies for removal of obstacles in water courses	LV and LT part of the basin
Water	Existing	Subsidies for cleaning of river beds	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Desired	Subsidies for erection of constructed wetlands	LV and LT part of the basin
Agriculture	Existing	Subsidies for improving drainage system performance	LV and LT part of the basin
Ecosystems	Desired	Subsidies for increasing organic carbon content in soil	LV and LT part of the basin

3.3 Case study Jiu

The design of the Jiu policy instrument for the SLNAE started with a preliminary inventory of the main policy documents for each WEFE sector based on desk research conducted by the CS lead. The policy documents were selected based on the following reasoning:

- The selection of policy documents for the water sector was guided by the documents transposing the Water Framework and Flood Risk Directives into Romanian legislation. Accordingly, the main policy documents considered for the analysis were the Jiu River Basin and Jiu Flood Risk Management Plans.
- The energy sector is covered in the policy inventory by the National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030 (PNIESC) that, although currently under revision, provides a good background to foster WEFE nexus governance.
- For the food sector, the Common Agricultural Policy National Strategic Plan 2023-2027 (PNS) is considered the leading policy document, setting the national targets for competitive, resilient agriculture as well as the sustainable development of rural areas. The document also considers climate action, the protection of natural resources, circular economy, and the preservation/improvement of biodiversity.
- Additionally, the Integrated Strategy for the Jiu Valley developed within the European Just Transition Mechanism was included in the policy inventory because the North part of the Jiu river basin is one of the European territories under transition to climate neutrality based on economic diversification and reconversion that will impact the WEFE nexus.
- Finally, the National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2030 was included in the policy inventory as it is considered an umbrella policy document setting the national targets for sustainable development goals and framing actions for reaching them.

The above policy inventory was preliminary discussed with stakeholders in the first NEXOGENESIS workshop, bilaterally during the governance assessment interviews and extensively in the second stakeholder workshop in October 2022. In parallel, the CS lead

preliminary identified policy instruments potentially relevant to include in the SLNAE tool derived from the selected policy documents.

During the third stakeholder workshop in May 2023, the policy instruments and targets (identified based on the existing ones such as the increase in irrigated areas, extension of public networks for water supply, increase of renewable energy share in the energy mix, etc.) were discussed, ranked, and validated by the stakeholders.

During the validation process, the stakeholders additionally recommended including policy documents on circular economy in the policy packages. The national strategy for circular economy was adopted at the end of 2022, the action plan is under development and instruments for its operationalization will be activated towards end of 2023.

Furthermore, some of the selected policy documents are currently under review/update (e.g. PNIESC) and several of the financing instruments are not yet finalized (e.g. PNS). These policies and instruments are expected to be finalized in Romania towards the end of 2023. Accordingly, the validated set of policy instruments, related goals and targets will be finalized in the coming months. These adjustments are not expected to delay the development of the Jiu SDM and of the SLNAE as WP3 and WP4 activities are distributed over year 3 of the project starting with the front runners CSs. This gives to the followers CSs such as Jiu more time to finalize their policy instruments. If, however, a delay in governmental policy processes occurs, the final instruments, goals and targets will be defined with the stakeholders based on the current political discussions. The process carried out to date resulted in the stakeholders validated policy instruments presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Stakeholders validated policy instruments for the Jiu case study

Sector that adopts/ implements the policy	Existing vs. desired policy	Policy instrument
Water	Jiu River Basin Management Plan; Existing	Investment in water saving measures in agriculture and domestic uses (e.g., water meters)
Water	Jiu River Basin Management Plan; Existing	Investments in new water outlets
Water	Jiu River Basin Management Plan; Existing	Investments to extend the water supply networks
Water	Jiu River Basin Management Plan; Existing	Investments in ecosystem restoration to achieve good ecological status
Water	Jiu River Basin Management Plan; Existing	Investments in the protection of wetlands and of peat bogs
Water	Jiu River Basin Management Plan; Existing	Investments in removing obstacles in the water courses and restoration of riparian habitats
Energy	National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030 PNIESC; Existing (in updating process)	Investments for extension of renewable energy infrastructure

Energy	National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030 PNIESC; Existing (in updating process)	Investments in co-generation units
Energy	National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030 PNIESC; Existing (in updating process)	Improvement of wastewater treatment capacity
Agriculture (including adaptation to climate change)	National Strategic Plan 2023-2027 (CAP); Existing	Investment for extension of irrigated area
Agriculture (including adaptation to climate change)	National Strategic Plan 2023-2027 (CAP); Existing	Subsidies and grants for natural protection curtains
Agriculture (including adaptation to climate change)	National Strategic Plan 2023-2027 (CAP); Existing	Subsidies and grants for buffer zones on agricultural land in the proximity of the water protection areas where the use of fertilizers and chemical products is forbidden
Sustainable Development	National Strategy for Sustainable development 2030; Existing	Investments in water reuse infrastructure
Sustainable Development	National Strategy for Sustainable development 2030; Existing	Investments in water distribution system
Sustainable Development	National Strategy for Sustainable development 2030; Existing	Investments in climate change adaptation and disaster risk prevention, resilience considering eco-system-based approaches
Sustainable Development	National Strategy for Sustainable development 2030; Existing	Investments in the protection and preservation of nature, biodiversity, and green infrastructure, including in urban areas, and reducing all forms of pollution
Sustainable Development	National Strategy for Sustainable development 2030; Existing	Investments in green-blue infrastructure to increase urban resilience to climate change, restoration of biodiversity, reduction of the carbon footprint, adequate management of water and soil, improved air quality
Transition towards a climate-neutral economy	Just Transition Mechanism, Jiu Valley Strategy; Existing	Investments in the development of small capacities for production, transport, and storage of RES energy for own consumption

3.4 Case Study Adige

The design the Adige policy instruments for the SLNAE, started with the CS leads identifying the WEFE nexus performance goals per WEFE sector to be included in the policy packages template. The results of the governance assessment, policy inventory, conceptual model, and local news items helped identifying these goals. Linking the WEFE nexus performance goals to the drought of the past few years increased interest of stakeholders to participate in the development of the policy instruments via bilateral meetings and at the NEXOGENESIS workshops.

Then, the policy inventory was used to select the policy objectives and targets associated with the nexus performance goals. The Adige river basin is managed by three different administrative entities, each with different policies and objectives (province of Bolzano, province of Trento, and Veneto region). Therefore, the policy objectives are identified per administrative region. Some policy objectives were defined only for one part of the basin, but relevant for either the entire basin or parts of it. These objectives were added after discussions amongst the CS leads and their colleagues and experts on the Adige river basin.

Following this, the CS leads developed numerical targets for the policy objectives. The analyzed policies in the policy inventory often did not provide numerical targets. Therefore, the CS leads prepared policy instruments that were used to consult the key stakeholders to design targets. This occurred either via email or through bilateral discussions.

Last, the policy instruments were validated during the third stakeholders' workshop in early July 2023. The validated policy instruments will be discussed with WP3 and WP4 for modeling feasibility and the goals and targets will be finalized in the coming months once the instruments will be consolidated. The process carried out to date resulted in the stakeholders validated policy instruments presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Stakeholders validated policy instruments for the Adige case study

Sector that adopts/ implements the policy	Existing vs. desired policy	Policy instrument	Scale of implementation
Agriculture	Existing	Subsidies to farmers for the adoption of more water-efficient irrigation technologies	South Tyrol part of the river basin
			Trentino part of the river basin
			Veneto part of the river basin
Agriculture	Existing	Incentives for saving water (requires introducing flow meters + Integrated information system)	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Agriculture	Existing		Trentino part of the river basin
Agriculture	Desired		Veneto part of the river basin

Agriculture	Desired	Incentives to farmers for crop conversion	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Agriculture	Desired		Trentino part of the river basin
Agriculture	Existing		Veneto part of the river basin
Energy	Desired	Regulations on hydropower production	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Energy	Existing		Trentino part of the river basin
Energy	Desired		Veneto part of the river basin
Energy	Existing	Incentives for PV installation	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Energy	Existing		Trentino part of the river basin
Energy	Desired		Veneto part of the river basin
Ecosystems	Existing	Regulation on status of the minimum ecological flow	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Ecosystems	Existing		Trentino part of the river basin
Ecosystems	Existing		Veneto part of the river basin
Ecosystems	Desired	Regulations on landscape diversity	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Ecosystems	Desired		Trentino part of the river basin
Ecosystems	Desired		Veneto part of the river basin
Water	Existing	Adjusting water withdrawal regulation for agriculture (requires: introducing flow meters + Integrated information system)	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Water	Existing		Trentino part of the river basin
Water	Existing		Veneto part of the river basin
Water	Existing	Public investment to construct new water reservoirs	South Tyrol part of the river basin
Water	Existing		Trentino part of the river basin
Water	Existing		Veneto part of the river basin
Water	Desired	Integrated information system on salt wedge intrusion	Veneto part of the river basin

3.5 Case study Inkomati-Usunthu

The first step in designing the Inkomati-Usunthu policy instruments for the SLNAE was to create an inventory of relevant policies to the WEFE nexus. These policies were reported in the policy inventory and presented to the stakeholders during the first stakeholder workshop in March 2022.

During this workshop, the stakeholders provided feedback on the identified policies and suggested additional ones. The policies from which to identify the policy instruments were narrowed down by the CS leads based on whether they contained specific quantitative targets, as this would make it easier to integrate them into the SLNAE.

The results of this exercise were presented to the stakeholders during the second stakeholder workshop in October 2022 where stakeholders were specifically asked to provide feedback on the targets identified in these policies. Moreover, the stakeholders were asked to suggest additional targets that are not included in existing policies. Based on this feedback, the CS leads further refined the list of policies, the related instruments and the quantitative targets. The CS leads then selected the indicator to ensure alignment between the targets and indicators.

Finally, at the third stakeholder workshop, the stakeholders were informed about the identified policy instruments, and they discussed them and selected the ones they preferred for inclusion in the SLNAE. The goals and targets will be finalized in the coming months. The process resulted in the policy instruments presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Stakeholders validated policy instruments for the Inkomati-Usunthu case study

Sector that adopts/ implements the policy	Existing vs. desired policy	Policy instrument
Food	Existing	Investments to set up inclusive local food value-chains
Ecosystem	Existing	Budget allocations and grants (public sector funding mechanisms) for protected area institutions to expand on protected areas
Ecosystem	Existing	Develop and strengthen economic incentives to encourage appropriate investment by the private sector in biodiversity management and conservation, such as tax incentives, conservation agriculture incentives to farmers and others
		Identification of priority areas for ecological infrastructure and national biodiversity priority areas (including freshwater ecosystem priority areas)
Water	Existing	Investment in reparation of water distribution and treatment infrastructure and in maintenance and monitoring of these systems to prevent leakage
		Monitoring of water usage to ensure effective water-supply planning, development and operation
Energy	Existing	REIPPP (power purchase program) that encourages renewable energy development

		Investments for cross-border energy transmission infrastructure to support regional electricity connection
Energy	Existing	Sectoral Emission Targets or SETs, which are quantitative greenhouse gas emission targets allocated to an emitting sector or sub-sector, over a defined time period
Water	Desired	Assignment of protected area status to surface water SWSAs
Food	Existing	Subsidize the most expensive input material for production systems that contribute most to food security
		Lower input costs where necessary by potentially reducing tariffs based on agreed terms between sector and relevant service providers
Food	Desired	Subsidies/incentives for adoption of more efficient irrigation techniques

4. Conclusion

As part of the activities of T1.4, this deliverable (D1.3) presented per each NEXOGENESIS CS, Nestos-Mesta, Lielupe, Jiu, Adige, and Inkomati-Usunthu, the stakeholder validated policies (i.e. policy instruments) for the SLNAE along with an illustration of the stakeholder co-creation and validation process. The policy packages template designed by WP1, in collaboration with WP3 and WP4, for the purpose of collecting the policy instruments and all necessary information for integrating them into the SDMs and SLNAE proved so far to be a helpful tool for the coordination of the CSs, their stakeholder preferences and WP3 and WP4 activities.

Next steps and further work

In the coming months the CSs will discuss the policy instruments presented in this report with WP3 and WP4 to identify those that are feasible, from a data and modelling perspective, to be integrated in the SLNAE and for which targets and indicators will be defined/ finalized. This process will result in the final set of policy instruments and related targets and indicators to be integrated in the SLNAE and whose impact on the WEF nexus stakeholders will be able to explore through the SLNAE tool. These activities will be reported in D3.4, D3.6, D4.2, D4.2 and D4.4.

References

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